

ASSESSMENT OF EXTERNAL RESPIRATORY FUNCTIONS IN PATIENTS WITH THYROID GLAND DISEASES ACCORDING TO THE LEVEL OF BRONCHIAL ASTHMA

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The etiology of bronchial asthma is different, it is widespread in the world, despite the availability of modern methods of treatment, frequent occurrence of severe complications, high risk of death is relevant. Autoimmune diseases of the thyroid gland are one of the main trigger factors in the development of bronchial asthma, and the combination of these two pathologies seriously harms the patient's health.

The purpose of the study evaluation of external respiratory functions in patients with thyroid diseases according to the degree of bronchial asthma .

Research materials and methods . Patients suffering from bronchial asthma and thyroid gland diseases make up the main group, they amount to 287 people. As a control group, only patients with bronchial asthma were recruited. In the main group, there were 50 patients with bronchial asthma of the 1st degree, 80 patients with the 2nd degree, 88 patients with the 3rd degree, and 69 patients with the 4th degree.

Research results . In grade 1 patients, FNH1 was 2.35 ± 0.3 in the main and control groups, respectively ; 2.1 ± 0.3 ; HTS 3.2 ± 0.3 ; 3.0 ± 0.3 ; Tiffno index 0.74 ± 0.02 ; It was equal to 0.70 ± 0.02 . FNH1 was 1.70 ± 0.3 among patients of the 2nd level; 1.85 ± 0.3 ; HTS 2.7 ± 0.3 ; 2.81 ± 0.3 ; Tiffno index 0.63 ± 0.02 ; 0.66 ± 0.02 ; FNH1 1.2 ± 0.3 in patients of the 3rd level; 1.49 ± 0.3 ; $r \geq 0.05$; HTS 2.23 ± 0.3 ; 2.49 ± 0.3 ; Tiffno index 0.54 ± 0.02 ; 0.6 ± 0.02 ; FNH1 0.72 ± 0.3 in patients of level 4; 0.96 ± 0.3 ; $r \geq 0.05$; HTS 1.78 ± 0.3 ; 2.01 ± 0.3 ; Tiffno index 0.41 ± 0.02 ; It was equal to 0.48 ± 0.02 .

Conclusion . A reliable difference was observed between the patients and the control group for FNH1 in grade 3-4. From this it can be understood that when bronchial asthma is observed together with thyroid diseases, external respiratory functions decrease in reliable values.

